

UNIVERSITY OF GHENT

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

National context: Protection against violence and moral or sexual harassment at work is provided under a federal law that dates from 11 June 2002. This law is not specific to research or higher education settings, it protects all types of workers, including those working at universities and research organisations administrative, technical, and research staff. This law provides a general framework, which is then implemented and, in some cases, further developed by some employers.

Regional context

In the Dutch-Speaking Community, a case in 2016 triggered debates in the Flemish Parliament in which the Minister of Education participated, as well as in the VLIR (Flemish Universities Council). This led to the development of a Charter on Transgressive Behaviour signed by the Minister of Education, expressing the commitment of Flemish higher education institutions (academic and non-academic) to developing a sustainable policy to address transgressive behaviour and provide guidelines for such policy at the institutional level. A Charter on Gender in Academia was then developed and signed by all Flemish universities in 2019. This charter covers all aspects of gender equality in academia including different types of gender-based violence. At present, a working group with representatives from different Flemish universities is evaluating the Charter on Transgressive Behaviour.

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

At UGhent, the policy mix relating to GBV consists of non-dedicated policies, that is, general policies addressing GBV as a part of the policy. The policy on tackling unwanted behaviour, hereinafter called the 'Unwanted Behaviour Policy' covers, but is not limited to, sexually transgressive behaviour and is part of the university's broader policy on wellbeing. The university considers it important to apply an integrated policy tackling psychosocial risks and wellbeing because different problems and their manifestations can be linked (e.g. stress can lead to substance abuse, which can trigger transgressive behaviour). It is the responsibility of the employer to prevent psychosocial risks (called primary prevention), to address risks (secondary prevention), and to deal with any harm done (tertiary prevention). In 2019, the existing 'Trustpunt' (Trust point) with confidential advisors for staff was broadened and opened to students. It is currently staffed by 8 people (7.6 FTE), and it is a place that students and personnel can turn to when facing issues related to psychosocial wellbeing. For staff, it deals with all the issues covered by the federal law from 2002; for students, it only deals with transgressive behaviour. The *Trustpunt* staff listen to anyone who turns to them and can offer advice and psychosocial education, can coach or mediate, and can initiate an intervention procedure involving a third party (e.g. through another service, but still within the university). In addition to the *Trustpunt* staff, there are confidential advisors available for staff (but not students). All issues and cases reported to a confidential advisor or to any person in a management position are expected to be reported to the *Trustpunt*, which keeps records and monitors what happens (quantitatively, but it also looks for any patterns in terms of behaviours that could be linked to certain individuals or to certain sites of the university). In addition to this policy, a Code of Conduct and an accompanying document with explanations and practical commentary, was developed by a multidisciplinary working group and adopted in 2018. It operationalises the university's vision relating to transgressive behaviour and is currently under revision to include anti-discrimination. The university's Work Regulations refer to this Code of Conduct, as do the Education and Examination regulations that students are required to sign. New employees are briefed on the Code of Conduct during their induction conversation when hired. They also receive a booklet with information about different psychosocial risks and the contact details of the *Trustpunt*. For staff, there are procedures that clearly set out the various options for reporting transgressive behaviour. Such procedures are still under development for students.

URLs

- › The Code of Conduct is available here: <https://www.ugent.be/student/nl/meer-dan-studeren/wel-in-je-vel/trustpunt/gedragscode-grensoverschrijdend-gedrag>
- › The other two policy documents are not publicly available. The Internal Procedure is given to employees as part of their employment contract and the Unwanted Behaviour Policy is available on the intranet.

Entry into force: The Code of Conduct (2018), the Internal Procedure (2012), the Unwanted Behaviour Policy (2017).

TRAINING

Staff receive support in the form of training and intervision, which involves exchanges between peers to reflect on their practices. There are also faculty confidential advisors available for staff. These are individuals chosen in a selection procedure who then receive three days of training and sign a confidentiality agreement. The university offers confidential advisors the opportunity to attend a monthly intervision moment and have a supervision moment twice per year. The *Trustpunt* also organises Active Bystander Training for the whole UGhent community, as well as more tailored sessions for different faculties.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

The role of RPOs in providing knowledge on GBV is limited to research commissioned by public authorities and work carried out by individual researchers. However, the University of Ghent is probably the main university contributing to the production of knowledge on GBV in Belgium. The International Centre for Reproductive Health of the University of Ghent and its experts are contributing to knowledge on this issue.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The three policies combined address the following **seven** forms of GBV: physical violence, psychological violence, sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender-based harassment, stalking and online violence. While all three policies address sexual violence and harassment, only the Code of Conduct (and its clarification document) and the Unwanted Behaviour policy address physical and online violence. The Code of Conduct is the only policy to address psychological violence, gender-based violence, and stalking.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: The three policies combined address all **7Ps**. While all three policies address protection, prosecution, and provision of services, the Internal Procedure and the Unwanted Behaviour Policy also address prevalence, partnership, and policy. Prevention is addressed in the Code of Conduct and in the Unwanted Behaviour Policy.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Specific vulnerable groups: The practical commentary on the Code of Conduct is the only policy out of the three that makes explicit reference to certain groups that cannot be expected or considered able to provide consent in the case of sexually transgressive behaviour – ‘... for example because of disease; mental, physical, or intellectual limitation; the influence of alcohol or drugs; or through intimidation and pressure’.

Intersectionality addressed: No.

Target groups

Unwanted Behaviour Policy

Academic staff
 Non-academic staff
 Students
 Other

Code of Conduct

Academic staff
 Non-academic staff
 Students
 Other

Internal Procedures

Academic staff
 Non-academic staff
 Other

Academic and non-academic staff and students are addressed in the documents. The Internal Procedure is the only one that does not address students. All policy documents also address other groups such as third parties (services, suppliers, visitors, etc.).

Bystanders addressed: Yes. All three policy documents invite bystanders to report via the same routes as victims. The Internal Procedure emphasises the protection of ‘whistle-blowers’ against retaliation.

Role of perpetrators addressed: Yes. The Code of Conduct addresses this indirectly as it states that the policy aims to be remedial and to ‘restore’ constructive relations and this attitude is therefore also expected from the parties involved. It also mentions that the *Trustpunt* is the first and main access point for everyone concerned and that includes persons lodging a complaint and the alleged perpetrator.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: Yes. The Internal Procedure and the Tackling Unwanted Behaviour Policy address monitoring. All cases are registered, coded, and reported on quantitatively in the quarterly and annual reports of the Service for Prevention at Work, which is in charge of the *Trustpunt*. These reports also include recommendations for addressing structural problems. Every five years, a survey is conducted among all staff on wellbeing at work and the survey includes a module on transgressive behaviour. As a follow-up to the survey results, a transversal action plan is drawn up along with action plans for each different part of the university (e.g. faculties, directorates). The *Trustpunt* is the actor responsible for implementing a number of these action plans and monitors on a yearly basis the implementation of the individual action plans of different parts of the university.

Evaluation: Yes. Policies and procedures are not formally evaluated but are informally evaluated on a yearly basis by the head of the Service of Prevention at Work and a number of internal stakeholders.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

The Internal Procedure set up institutional procedures for cases of GBV among staff members and where staff members have complaints against any third party. The Unwanted Behaviour Policy set up institutional procedures for cases of GBV among students, between staff and students, among staff and with third party.

Internal Procedure

The policy defines the procedure for the following:

Staff vs staff: Who to contact, how to report, a description of the investigation, time frame, responsible persons, outcomes, sanctions.

Prior to the procedure: the recommendation is to follow the 'normal' path to solving problems by talking to and having regular discussions with the individuals involved, possibly with the aid of a line manager or someone else.

Who to contact, how to report, responsible persons: 'In certain circumstances, it may be possible to request the intervention of parties that are more neutral and specifically trained for this purpose: a confidential advisor and a prevention advisor for psychosocial aspects. Then, a request for an informal procedure can be submitted either to the confidential advisor (and/or antenna) or (though this is suggested as a sort of 'higher step') to the prevention advisor for psychosocial aspects.

Description of the investigation: These actors will listen and provide advice. Information will be provided on possible next steps: either no action; or active intervention on the part of the confidential advisor/prevention advisor who will set up further consultations, seek help from another actor in the organisation, or arrange mediation between the parties involved if they agree. A next step (or if the complainant wishes to skip the informal phase this step can be immediately undertaken) is the formal phase, in which the prevention advisor must be formally asked to become involved by the complainant. If the complaint relates to unwanted behaviour, this is explicitly stated in the title of the request.

Time frame: The request must be followed by a formal consultation, which takes place within 10 days of the submission of a request for a prevention advisor to become involved. All the steps are officially documented. The next steps depend on whether the complaint relates to an act that is of a collective or an individual nature. In the case of formal interventions relating to unwanted behaviour, all acts, their location and time, and the identities of those involved are recorded in a document, and the request to the employer to take appropriate action is recorded. The document is signed and formally handed to the prevention advisor, who must countersign that the request has been received. The prevention advisor can refuse to accept the request if s/he deems the situation described in the submitted request as one that does not constitute violence, bullying, or unwanted sexual behaviour at work. The complainant must be notified of the rejection of the request within 10 calendar days of its submission. If the request is accepted, the prevention advisor informs the employer of the case and the identity of the complainant in writing. The employer is informed that the complainant is protected against reprisals for a duration of 1 year. The prevention advisor starts an investigation (comprising seven steps) and writes an advisory report (there are seven mandatory components in the report) that is submitted to the employer within three months and, if the complainant agrees, to the confidential advisor as well. This 3-month term can be extended once for another three months if duly justified. The report is explained to the employer, and then the complainant and other concerned person are informed in writing as soon as possible.

Outcome, sanctions: The prevention advisor for psychosocial aspects in charge of risks of violence informs the Prevention Advisor of the Internal Service for Prevention about the proposed prevention measures so that these can be integrated in the coordination actions of the Prevention Advisor of the Internal Service for Prevention. The employer has to assess the problem and make an action plan with measures. These may include individual measures against one or the other staff member (the procedures for the notification of which are also described). Within a maximum of two months after the advice to the employer by the prevention advisor for psychological risks, the Director for Governance Affairs must inform 1) the prevention advisor for psychosocial aspects, 2) the complainant and others directly concerned, 3) the Prevention Advisor, and 4) anyone else the employer deems useful about the employer's decisions and follow-up on the case in question. The decided measures are to be implemented asap by the employer. The procedure is not interrupted if the complainant leaves the organisation in the course of the process.

Other: Who to contact, how to report, responsible persons

The employer will refer the victim to the right bodies or people to contact for psychological support and follow-up on the case. In some cases, the employer or insurer will bear the financial costs of pursuing the case for the victim. There are provisions for making an official record of the case, if the victim wishes to (this is not done automatically), and the details of the report are kept confidential. A report is submitted to the victim's/the employee's immediate supervisor or 'permanence centre', and is then submitted to the *Trustpunt*, which 'in a joint agreement' will decide on further measures. A decision to take judicial steps can be taken jointly.

Unwanted Behaviour Policy

The policy defines the procedure for the following:

Student vs student: Who to contact, responsible persons

If mediation is requested, the *Trustpunt* or other university services will offer to act as a mediator for students.

The *Trustpunt* will listen and provide advice, and if requested it will inform the student/complainant/victim how to proceed further.

Student vs staff: Who to contact, how to report, responsible persons

A student who feels s/he has been a victim of unwanted behaviour from a staff member can contact a confidential advisor at any time to request that action be taken (e.g. by talking with the superior of the alleged perpetrator to request that the individual involved cease to engage in the unwanted behaviour), in which case the employer will talk with the other actor involved. There is no other information in this policy except a reference made to the 'procedures' (which are in a different document). If a student is the complainant, s/he cannot ask for a formal intervention (this option is only open to staff).

Staff vs staff: Who to contact, responsible persons, outcomes

This policy defines the procedure in the following terms and also refers to the procedures that are annexed to the employment contract: 'Reporting is possible through the *Trustpunt*. The confidential advisor will listen to the story, record the context, and enquire about the complainant's request/expectations for help. Agreements are put down in writing and signed by the complainant and the confidential advisor. There are three possibilities, which are described in detail in the Internal Procedure of UGhent for tackling psychosocial risks: 1) the complainant only wants to be listened to, advised, and/or counselled; 2) the complainant wants an attempt at mediation with the other person involved or with a person within the institution who can offer a solution; 3) the complainant wants to submit a request for a formal intervention, in which case s/he will always be referred to the external prevention advisor for psychosocial aspects in charge of risks of violence who can execute a formal investigation. After the formal report has been explained to the employer, the latter must take steps to stop the unwanted behaviour.'

Other: Who to contact, how to report, responsible persons, outcome

Who to contact, responsible persons: 'If a staff member or student feels he or she has been a victim of unwanted behaviour from a person external to the University of Ghent, this must be reported to the central reporting point. The Psychosocial Wellbeing unit records this information, in conformity with legal provisions, in the Register of Unwanted Behaviour by Third Persons. The employer must evaluate this, in conformity with the same legislation, and if appropriate take the necessary prevention measures. After being notified, the staff member or student will always be invited for a talk during which it will be determined whether and what action can be taken. If the complainant agrees, the employer is informed, who will decide what action is possible.'

How to report: There are well-defined procedures for reporting transgressive behaviour for staff but such procedures are under development for students. All the steps are laid out (with responsible actors and timelines); the responsible decision-makers are identified (the Rector is the final decision-maker); and potential sanctions are listed. The policy outlines the roles of 17 different actors, and the steps for three different 'phases' or scenarios: 1) the steps that can be taken prior to an internal procedure, 2) the informal phase of a procedure, and 3) the formal phase of a procedure. The actors in the internal procedure are: 1) rapporteur/complainant, 2) the other person

involved / accused, 3) witnesses, 4) third parties, 5) the psychosocial wellbeing unit, 6) the confidential advisor, 7) the antenna, 8) the prevention advisor for psychosocial aspects in charge of risks of violence, 9) the prevention advisor for health and safety risks – occupational physician, 10) the prevention advisor of the Internal Service for Prevention and Protection at Work, 11) the employer, 12) the sub-committee for Prevention and Protection at Work, 13) the Psychosocial Risks Advisory Group, 14) the director of the Directorate for Governance Affairs, 15) the director of the Directorate for Personnel and Organisation, 16) the hierarchical line, 17) colleagues.)

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This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

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